

THE NEEDS FOR MEDIA DEVELOPMENT OF PORLITE (LITERACY PORTAL) VIA GOOGLE SITES TO INCREASE THE STUDENT’S READING INTEREST

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Abstract

This research aimed to analyze the needs for media development of a portal media (literacy portal) via the Google Site to increase student’s interest in reading. The portal media is called Porlite. Porlite can be used to increase the ability to use digital technology in the world of education, especially during the implementation of school literacy movements. This portal media via the Google site can also increase student’s interest in reading and literacy skills. This type of research was quantitative-descriptive. The research subjects were students of SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. This research took a sample of 73 students from 286 populations in phase E. The research results showed that student’s interest in Porlite was 80%, while the needs for students to use Porlite as a literacy medium was 70%, and the relationship between Porlite and interest in reading was 72%. Porlite with Google Sites can be used in literacy activities to increase student’s interest in reading.

Keywords: Porlite, Google Sites, literacy portal, interest in reading, media literacy

INTRODUCTION

Literacy skills can be understood as a person’s ability to read and write. Literacy mastery is an important indicator for improving the achievements of the younger generation in achieving success (Kazemier et al., 2021; Liang et al., 2021; Flierl & Maybee, 2020; Lupo et al., 2024; Papadopoulou et al., 2023). Instilling literacy as early as possible must be realized because it is the main capital in creating an intelligent and cultured nation (Barratt et al., 2024; Cary et al. 2024; DePauw et al., 2019; Hirsh et al., 2018; Scharrer et al., 2023; Baker et al., 2019; Gellel, 2018). Literacy activities cannot be separated from reading activities.

Reading is one of the language skills that students need to have in addition to the other three language skills. Reading activities for students are not only carried out during

classroom learning but can be carried out in the school library during free time. Reading activities can also be done at home with guidance from parents. Getting into the habit of reading is very important (Syafitri, 2019; Prabowo et al., 2024; Firmas et al., 2021; Mushtaq et al., 2021; Altamura et al., 2023).

Getting students used to reading activities is certainly not easy, so when students get used to reading activities, they need an interest in reading. The interest in reading is a strong desire accompanied by a person’s efforts to read. Students who have a strong interest in reading will be seen in their willingness to spend time doing frequent reading activities (Akmal et al., 2020; Widiana et al., 2023; Kikas et al., 2017; Liu et al., 2024; Wang et al., 2018; Zhao et al., 2018; Wang et al., 2023). For students who do not yet have a strong interest in reading, reading will not

Submitted	Accepted	Published
17-02-2024	21-09-2024	15-10-2024

be an important activity to do.

Interest in reading is directly proportional to the level of educational progress of a nation. Reading activities are very important for the progress of a nation. The quality parameters of a nation can be seen from the condition of its education. Education is always related to learning activities (Lesmana et al., 2019; Batubara, 2023; Fathoni et al., 2017; Faisal, 2023; Syaifullah et al., 2024; Nasution et al., 2024).

Learning is always synonymous with reading activities because reading will increase a person's knowledge, attitudes, and skills (Elgort et al., 2018; Stainthorp, 2020; Mimeau et al., 2018; Qiao et al., 2023). Reading purpose is nothing but a step in obtaining facts, ideas, and knowledge/stories so that you can conclude what you read, be able to group or classify, be able to assess/evaluate, and be able to compare or contrast (Tarigan, 1985).

According to statistical data from UNESCO, the interest in reading or basic literacy of Indonesian people was very worrying, namely only 0.001%. That means, out of 1,000 Indonesians, there was only 1 person who reads diligently and is willing to apply basic literacy. In research titled World's Most Literate Nations Ranked conducted by Central Connecticut State University in 2020, Indonesia was ranked 60th out of 61 countries with low literacy levels. Meanwhile, Finland ranks first in literacy level (almost 100%). This data showed that Indonesia is still far behind Singapore and Malaysia in terms of basic literacy.

The Indonesian government has established a school literacy movement since 2016. The School Literacy Movement (GLS) can be a means to recognize, understand, and gain knowledge for students at school. Through the literacy movement, students can also develop character in everyday life (Kurnia, 2021; Mayuni et al., 2020; Sihalohe et al., 2019; Setiyadi, 2018; Firdaus, 2021; Pratiwi et al., 2022). This literacy movement program is also able to strengthen the movement to develop character as stated in Minister of Education and Culture Regulation Number 23 of 2015. One of the activity programs is the 15-minute activity of reading a book that is not a textbook before study time begins.

GLS is an effort that is carried out

comprehensively and sustainably to make schools become learning organizations that have lifelong literate citizens by involving the community. One of the goals of this school literacy movement is to increase student's awareness that reading is very important and brings broader insight (Oktaviani & Sopiah, 2020; Wuryandani et al., 2019; Putri et al., 2024; Anugerahwati, 2019; Walipah et al., 2020).

However, the implementation of the literacy program, which is a national program, has not yet had a significant impact on students' interest in reading. This requires special attention from all parties so that the problem of interest in reading can be resolved immediately. The low interest in reading among children is caused by several things, such as unattractive titles and contents of books, and expensive book prices so that those with a mediocre income cannot afford to buy books to meet their reading needs (Prawiyogi et al., 2020; Zur et al., 2022; Amaliah et al., 2024; Gusnetti et al., 2022).

Based on interviews and observations conducted at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung, the literacy movement that has been implemented at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung, namely reading 15 minutes before learning begins, was still not running effectively. Carrying out literacy activities for 15 minutes in the morning before learning begins was more likely to be used by students to look at Android. This was because, firstly, there were no standard guidelines for implementing literacy activities, so teachers can only instruct literacy activities as they pleased, without any feedback from literacy activities. Second, there were not enough reading books available, teachers only instructed reading books brought by students, while some students preferred not to bring books. Third, the availability of reading materials was minimal in libraries.

The development of school literacy programs needs special attention so that it can be optimized by all school members. In order to carry out literacy activities effectively. So, the research aimed to analyze the needs for media development Porlite (literacy portal) to increase student's interest in reading at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung.

METHOD

This type of research was quantitative-descriptive. The research subjects were class X

phase E students of SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung, Dharmasraya Regency, West Sumatra, Indonesia. The population of the research was 286 students. Based on Formula (1), the number of samples used in the research was 73 students in phase E of SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung.

$$n = \frac{N}{N \cdot d^2 + 1} \quad (1)$$

n = Sample size

N = Population size

d = Percentage of error allowance due to sampling (10%)

The data collected was based on a questionnaire instrument. A questionnaire is a data collection technique that asks questions or written statements to respondents to answer (Sugiyono, 2016). This research used a direct questionnaire with closed questions, namely with answers to the questions asked and available. The data analysis technique used was descriptive analysis. The data obtained was analyzed based on a range of values with scoring such as in Table 1.

Table 1 Data Scoring

Score	Value
90-100	Very high
80-89	High
65-79	Moderate
55-64	Low
0-54	Very low

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Based on observations in the field, the implementation of the literacy movement at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung was still not optimal. According to the results of interviews with teachers, the reasons for not implementing literacy activities were there are no clear guidelines and no complete reading sources available. So, student's interest in reading was low.

At the initial needs analysis stage, research results identified that students were not interested in reading because it was difficult to find interesting reading material. When the literacy movement was carried out for 15 minutes in the morning, students were more inclined to play Android. So, the school literacy movement was not running well.

Based on the results of initial observations, the author was interested in designing digital literacy media. Therefore, the

author was trying to develop a media on the Google site, which will provide reading material and columns to inspire. The media that will be developed is called Porlite (literacy portal). The design of Porlite will contain several menus for literacy activities so that students can find reading materials that they like. Porlite media can be accessed by all students. The features that can be accessed by students are Literacy Materials (fiction and non-fiction), Literacy Games, Our Work, and Gallery. Porlite not only provides reading sources to be read, but students can express ideas for writing. The reading materials that will be provided at Porlite are readings that students like. These readings will be published according to the student's wishes. Before the authors carried out the research, the authors carried out a speed analysis. Therefore, the authors designed a questionnaire consisting of three topics which had several questions.

Needs analysis was researched based on the number of samples and population at SMAN 1 Pulau Punjung. This can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2 The Research Population

Class	The Number of Students
Phase E1	35 students
Phase E2	34 students
Phase E3	35 students
Phase E4	34 students
Phase E5	33 students
Phase E6	34 students
Phase E7	34 students
Phase E8	29 students
Total	268 students

Table 2 showed the population of the research. Based on Formula (1), the research sample used was 73 students. Through a needs analysis questionnaire consisting of three variables on student interests and needs and the relationship between social media and student's reading interests. Then, the following results were obtained.

Figure 1 showed that from the 3 question variables given, almost all students expressed interest and need and stated the relationship between social media and student's interest in reading. The results of the initial research following the analysis of the questionnaire that has been distributed, so that the variable of interest in Porlite reached a very high range of 4 students and for the need for media 4 students, while the variable of the relationship between Porlite and interest in reading 16 students. In the

high range, the attractiveness variable answers 20 students' needs, 16 students' needs, and 21 students' relationships. Meanwhile, the medium range for the attractiveness and needs variables was 30 students and for the relationship variable, it was 23 students. While the lowest range was 2 students.

Figure 1 The Results of Needs Analysis

Table 3 The Results of the Questionnaire

Indicator	Percentage
Interest in Porlite via Google Sites.	70.4%
The needs for Porlite (literacy portal) media through Google Sites as a literacy forum.	80.6%
Porlite's relationship with interest in reading.	71.6%

Based on Table 3, student's interest in social media or literacy portals via the Google Sites reached 70.4%. The percentage of indicators of the needs for Porlite (literacy portal) media via the Google Sites reached 80.6%. Meanwhile, the relationship between social media and interest in reading reached 71.6%. Thus, it can be concluded that the use of literacy portal media is very necessary for students to improve their abilities. This strengthens the results of previous research which states that the media used in the learning process can improve student's abilities and learning outcomes (Supardi et al., 2023; Arpan et al., 2016; Feladi et al., 2017; Budiman et al., 2022; Sulistiyarini et al., 2018; Hernando et al., 2022).

The inferential analysis indicates that after the implementation of media literacy, there was a significant increase in student's interest in reading at school. This was supported by the results of statistical tests showing a significant difference between the conditions before and after the media literacy intervention, with student's values lower than the set significance level. Therefore, it can be

concluded that the use of media literacy has a positive impact that can motivate students to be more active in reading and improve their literacy skills. These findings emphasize the importance of integrating media literacy into the learning approach to stimulate student's interest in reading and enhance their overall literacy. Thus, it can be concluded that based on the analysis of the needs for developing Porlite, the literacy portal media, students felt very interested and need it and it was related to their interest in reading.

CONCLUSION

According to results and discussion, students felt very interested if Porlite is applied in the learning process. This can be seen from the questionnaire indicators filled out by students, where 70.4% of students were interested in Porlite, 80.6% of students needed Porlite, and 71.6% of students were interested in reading using Porlite.

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